

ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES CONTENTS.

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Abstract: My current research is an attempt to understand English for Specific Purposes (ESP). A very important area of ELT by embracing the efforts of various linguists to define it. We trace its historical growth, discuss its characteristics, and try to understand its scope. It is intended to address the specific needs of EFL/ESL learners. Many conflicting opinions have been reported on the definition of ESP, but there seems to be some consensus. Finally, it is limited to teaching English to learners with specific goals and purpose: These goals may be professional, academic, or scientific in nature.

Keywords: English for specific purposes, characteristics, specific needs, authentic material

An extremely important area of discussion among ESP researchers has been the inclusion of specialized contents in ESP courses. The first phase of ESP that lasted till the beginning of 1960's, confined itself to the teaching materials consisted of authentic texts in different fields of specialization (Hutchinson and Waters, 1987). Furthermore "S" stands for "specific" suggests that ESP "can be differentiated from general EFL/ESL by its concern with specialized language and practice"(Hadley, 2006, p. 3). Wales (1993, p. 4) presented the following "specific factors of pedagogical concern" while discussing the reasons of including general English in workplace (ESP) courses.

"They are:

1. that there are linguistic relationships between general and specific English.
2. that learners' perceived needs may include general as well as specific English.
3. that learners' L2 proficiency level may require general skill development".

St. Johns and Dudley-Evans (1991, p. 307) contended that ESP includes "all courses in specialized language and practice". It has been stated that "if a subject such as medicine or computing is taught in English, this is not in itself ESP teaching; it is content teaching. ESP has to involve teaching of the language as well as the skills associated with --- EGAP ---- ESAP" (Dudley-Evans, 1997, p. 9). Inclusion of contents of target subjects seems an integral part of any ESP program. "The contents of teaching materials should be relevant to their needs and also convey new information for students" (Chantrupanth, 1993, p. 9). Adamson (1997, p. 65) explained his experience of developing and teaching ESP course for nurses at Miyagi University and concluded that "ESP through content

is a viable and even preferable way to approach language teaching". Special subject contents serve several purposes that are "sometimes to motivate learners, sometimes to ensure learners are able to understand the underlying conceptual features the language is describing" (Cozens, 2006, p. 7). He offered useful insights into the attitude of several teachers who did not want to include subject contents and believed that "an academic study skill program" or a "general language program" could fulfill the specific needs of all learners. Gunawardena and Knight (1989) discussed about the learners' negative attitude towards general English courses at the engineering and medical faculties in Sri Lankan universities. He presented his findings that "the students feel that the study of "general English" is a waste of time, and they have little or no tolerance for material outside their field of study" (ibid., p. 112). The same attitude has been more candidly defined as follows: Languages at tertiary level are often treated as second-rate subjects. This situation is reflected in students' attitude towards language as a faculty subject which they consider a necessary evil, but not linked to what they believe to be their genuine study program (Cozens, 2006 cf. Gvardjancic, 2001, p. 8). Several research studies were conducted and their findings proved that ELT courses that did not include subject contents adversely affected learners' motivation. Peters and Saxon (1997, p. 108) provided insights into their experience of creating content-based units for a first-year introductory art history course at a leading university in Japan and concluded that "content-based English classes can provide a meaningful context for the development of English language skills". Sagliano et al. (1998) have also interpreted their findings and suggested that specific contents should be included in ESP teaching materials. Though the role of an ESP practitioner should not be limited to the content teaching only and research has suggested that it is not limited to the students' perception but also affects members of other faculties and administrative personnel, too, who often see the role of ESP teacher simply as a way to instill relevant lexical items into their students" (Cozens, 2006 cf. Smoak, 2004, p. 8). An ESP program that is strictly confined to the specialized subject content is also undesirable and Cozens (2006: 10 cf. Davis, 1979) has warned "of the danger that totally content-based course can have on the health of learners". He gave the example of an anteater that was fed only on protein at an English zoo which suggested that the language learners needed "to have experience beyond the language learning classroom to provide the roughage necessary to enjoy using English in a natural context" (ibid.: 10). Hutchinson and Waters (1987) have also reported that ESP is not restricted to teaching only specialized

varieties of English. "Relevant lexical items" constitute an integral part of an ESP course and Bejan (1989, p. 94) suggested a practical "division of vocabulary words into three classes: technical, sub technical and nontechnical". This seemed to offer valuable insights into the fact that an ideal ESP course should strike a balance between these two extremes: general English courses and strictly content-based language courses. Gatehouse (2001) has proposed that "three abilities" are required by the learners to handle a professional target communicative situation: ability to use special jargon, ability to use general academic or business skills and the ability to communicate in any other social setting. This comprehensive objective can be effectively achieved through an ESP course that includes subject contents and general English. Fiorito (2005, p. 2) advocated that "ESP combines subject matter and English language teaching". He has concluded that such a combination is highly motivating because it.

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